
The Effect of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention with Mediation of Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction: Study on Netflix Application Users

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Abstract

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This research focuses on the role of brands in increasing repurchase intention through good relationships and trust formed with consumers. This study aimed to examine and analyze the effect of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention on the Netflix application through the mediation of Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction. The population used in this study are consumers who have subscribed to the Netflix application and are aged less than 20 to 50 years and over. The sampling technique in this study was random sampling. The sample used in this study was 200 respondents. The analytical method used in this study is Partial Least Square (PLS) using the Smart Modeling Partial Least Squares application. The results showed that the two independent variables, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and the mediating variables, Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction, significantly affected the repurchase intentions of Netflix application subscribers. The two independent variables, Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use, significantly affect Continuance Intention. Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction can provide a Partial Mediation role (partially mediate) on the relationship between Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use towards the Continuance Intention of Netflix application customers.

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1. Introduction

The rapid development of internet technology directly impacts one's life. The internet broadly influences various aspects, ranging from communication, work, entertainment, and transportation. Indonesia itself has an increasing number of internet users from year to year. The development of the internet, according to the databooks.co.id website (2021) data obtained at the end of March 2021, internet users in Indonesia reached 76.8% of the total population. There are 212.3 million internet users out of Indonesia's estimated population of 274.9 million. This data is very different compared to the previous two years' data obtained from the Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) which shows that the number of urban internet users reached 53.2%. In contrast, the number of rural internet users reached 3%.

Figure 1. Statistics of Internet Users in Indonesia
Source: wearesocial.com, 2020

Of Indonesia's 212.3 million internet users, 75% are dominated by Generation Y and Z. This generation has an age range between 15-40 years. Nearly 95% of this generation access the internet via smartphone. Meanwhile, most of them access social media content and online videos. Another trend is accessing news and science channels. This fact is supported by the ease of accessing the internet or Wi-Fi in various places. Currently, it is straightforward to find boarding houses and apartments with Wi-Fi facilities, such as cafes and restaurants; many private homes also use Wi-Fi. The ease with which the public can access the internet cannot be separated from extraordinary global events (KLB), namely the Covid-19 pandemic, which has spread since early 2020. The need for internet access has become irreplaceable because educational activities from elementary to tertiary levels are online. Alternatively, online, as well as work in offices, employees can do their work from home, which is known as WFH or Work from Home

Figure 2 Age Profile of Internet Users in Indonesia
Source: wearesocial.com, 2020

The Indonesian market itself means something other than that the Netflix application can dominate the Indonesian market easily. The survey results show that Netflix lost to the SVOD application that was launched in September 2020, namely Disney+ Hotstar. According to a survey conducted by Media Partner Asia (MPA) from the SVOD market share platform, Disney+ Hotstar ranks first in the number of subscribers in Indonesia with 2.5 million subscribers, followed by Viu with 1.5 million, Vidio with 1.1 million, and Netflix has 950 thousand subscribers.

Figure 3 SVOD Competition in Indonesia Q4 2020
Source: justwatch.com, 2020

Netflix has a problem in the form of a decrease in the number of users who decide not to use Netflix again. The first factor that makes Netflix lose is the problem of sharing passwords or passwords for sharing Netflix accounts with other people who don't live in the same house. Currently, Netflix alone estimates that there are 222 million households that pay to access its video-on-demand service, but, on the other hand, access to Netflix accounts is also shared with more than 100 million additional households, through the habit of sharing accounts. Netflix's policy that allows sharing of extra accounts for families, but prohibits the practice of sharing accounts in any other way. Netflix plans to charge additional fees for users who frequently share accounts outside their family, to watch movies on Netflix. The second factor is the Russian invasion of Ukraine. After the war broke out, Netflix decided to stop its service in Russia. The decision also suspended all paid subscriptions in Russia, causing Netflix to lose 700,000 paid subscribers who decided not to continue subscribing from the Red Bear Country, if it does not suspend its service in Russia, Netflix estimates that the company will still see subscriber growth of up to 500,000 in this quarter. The third factor is the problem of increased competition. Netflix said that the launch of a movie streaming application by another entertainment company also played a role in the decline in its subscribers in the first quarter of 2022. Reported in BBC news in 2022 Netflix reported the number of subscribers who decided not to continue their subscription by almost 1 million during April-July. This number is still less than the previous projection of two million.

SVOD companies require continuance intention as an important factor to retain customers and play an important role in facing challenges and dynamic competition. In the digital industry it is known that the cost of attracting new users or customers is higher than through traditional channels. Benefits in using services, especially digital services can grow faster after users have made transactions and experienced digital experiences themselves. SVOD application users tend to spend more time and money than when they first interact or use the service. It can be said that the growth of the SVOD application industry will be positive, if the company is able to maintain a high continuance intention. According to Hampton-Sosa (2019) continuance intention can be interpreted as an intention to continue in the future and can be interpreted as repeat purchases for satisfied customers.

Hasan (2017), in his research, stated that a continuance intention is a form of a customer's intention to use digital technology in the future. Continuance intention is expected to arise from SVOD application users. The better the continuance intention of application users, the company can achieve large profits without incurring additional costs for promotion. The low user interest in the SVOD application influences the user's decision to use the service. The company will lose out if the user only tries the application once without intending to re-subscribe. Theoretically, this object will be more easily approached using the Theory of Acceptance Model (TAM). TAM includes theories related to individual perceptions of using different types of technology (Camilleri & Falzon, 2020). TAM theory explains whether individuals accept or reject technology. TAM is a development of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) formulated by Fishbein and Ajzen (1991). In the context of SVOD applications, two independent variables can be used to explain the relationship between TAM and Intention to Use. These independent variables are Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU).

Perceived Usefulness (PU) is the level of one's belief in the usefulness of a product. Perceived Usefulness (PU) determines whether an individual can accept technology to assist in carrying out work/activities. Thompson (1991) states that individuals will use information technology if the individual understands the overall benefits or usefulness. Furthermore, Thompson concluded that the benefits of information technology positively affect IT users in carrying out their duties. The intention of consumer behavior in the object of this research, the usefulness of the SVOD application to its users, will affect the customer's intention to subscribe. Prospective customers can then assess the SVOD application in terms of benefits and usability with costs incurred. If the usefulness value is high, they will not hesitate to subscribe because they feel the platform application positively impacts them.

According to Faqih (2016), Perceived Usefulness is a significant fundamental framework of consumer behavior and the primary motivator for accepting new technology (IS/IT Acceptance). Furthermore, in a large spectrum of research on the adoption of new technology, if someone believes that the new system can help improve performance, skills, and knowledge, then it can automatically stimulate one's perceptions and behavior to be involved in adopting and using the technology. Previous studies have shown that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly affect the intention to continue using (Continuance Intention). Research conducted by Camilleri & Falzon (2020); Faqih (2016); Hampton-Sosa (2019); Hasan (2017) stated that the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in the SVOD application has a significant effect on the intention to use. Some studies show the opposite results. Research conducted by Lee & Lim (2019); Leowarin & Thanasuta (2021); Pal & Triyason (2018) stated that TAM in SVOD applications has no significant effect on the intention to use.

Research conducted by Fernandes & Guerra (2019); Guerra (2015) shows that perceived value can be a link between the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and subscription intentions. Fernandes & Guerra (2019) in their research stated that perceived usefulness has a significant effect on perceived value. Research conducted by Haba, Hassan, & Dastane (2017); Wang (2014) shows that perceived ease of use positively affects perceived value. Research conducted by Wang (2014) states that perceived value can mediate mobility, perceived security, ease of use, and usefulness variables on customer satisfaction and trust. This research takes the object of government access to online applications. Perceived value positively affects the intention to use the application (Lien, Wen, & Wu, 2011); (Singh, Singh, Kalinić, & Liébana-Cabanillas, 2021). In the context of streaming services, research conducted by Singh, Singh, Kalinić, & Liébana-Cabanillas (2021) states that perceived value can mediate the relationship between convenience, monetary, emotional, and social value on continuance intention.

Factors that strengthen the relationship between perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use towards the intention to resubscribe (continuance intention), a second mediating variable is needed besides perceived value. This phenomenon is related to the ultimate goal of this research, namely the customer's desire to extend application subscriptions or not. To achieve a more substantial level of intention besides cognitive aspects (perceived value), affective aspects are also needed. Affective conditions are related to emotional responses, both positive and negative, to a condition. In the context of this research, the object is the SVOD application. The affective condition in question is pleasure, satisfaction, and love. Customer satisfaction relates to consumer behavioral intentions. If potential customers are satisfied with the benefits and convenience of the application, it will be easier for potential customers to decide to use the application. Customer satisfaction is an essential variable in measuring customer value performance because related application companies can assess the extent to which the customer's response is whether to accept or reject. In the modern era's theory and practice of marketing, customer satisfaction is an important concept for customers so that they can provide company benefits through repeated purchases (Hsu, Raj, & Sandy, 2021).

Research conducted by Cheah, Isa, & Yang, (2021); Amin, *et.al* (2015); Lim, (2017) state that perceived usefulness have a positive effect on customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, perceived ease of use is also known to have a positive relationship with customer satisfaction (Ohk, Park, & Hong, 2015); (Shah & Attiq, 2016); (Tu, Fang, & Lin, 2012). Customer satisfaction is also an essential determinant for marketers to determine customer loyalty, repeat sales, positive WOM, and company profits (Annaraud & Berezina, 2020)

Research conducted by Hsu *et al.*, (2021); Pratiwi & Dwiyanto, (2019) stated that customer satisfaction influences consumer behavioral intentions. Both studies take the same object, namely digital music applications. Research similar to the company's commercial website objects shows that perceived usefulness and ease of use significantly affect customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction also significantly affects visitor behavioral intentions (Sik & Lee, 2010). Kaur & Gopinathan (2019) stated three critical factors related to the assessment of customer satisfaction in digital music applications. These three are system quality, trust, and information quality. It was concluded that customer satisfaction could be the second mediating variable after perceived value. This research analyzes the effect of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention by Mediation of Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction: Studies on Netflix Application Users.

2. Materials and Methods

This research was conducted to test and confirm theories in science. This research uses explanatory research or explanatory research. This research is a survey about the intention to continue using (continuance intention) users of the Netflix platform. At the same time, the time chosen to conduct the research was March 2022. The population in this study were all people who had used the Netflix application. While the population in this study is not known with certainty, the opportunity for each member of the population to be sampled is different. Respondents to this study are a sample of people who are old enough to subscribe to Netflix, namely 18 years and over and have subscribed to Netflix for at least one month. Then this is to the research sample size suggestion from Malhotra (2012), namely for marketing research, at least a minimum number of respondents is required of 200 respondents. The data collection method explains the data types, sources, and fact-collection techniques used in this study. In this study, the primary data is the survey results from the research questionnaire, which includes indicators such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived value, customer satisfaction, and continuance intention. Primary data sources are individual respondents, online forms, and focus groups. This study's secondary data sources are literature, articles, journals, and internet sites related to this research. Furthermore, an analysis of

the data that has been collected is carried out so that the data can complement one another. Data collection was carried out by giving questionnaires to each respondent so that the respondents understood the statement of research indicators well. The procedure for implementing the questionnaire distribution was carried out using the Google form, bearing in mind that direct distribution of the questionnaire carries a relatively high risk of transmission of Covid-19. The data analysis technique used in this study is Partial Least Square (PLS). Partial Least Square (PLS) is a variant-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) model. Specifically, the application used is SmartPLS. SmartPLS uses the bootstrapping method or random multiplication, so the assumption of normality will not be a problem in SmartPLS.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Results

Data processing techniques using the Partial Least Square (PLS) based SEM method. The PLS software in this study used software developed at the University of Hamburg, Germany, which was named SMARTPLS version 3.3.3. In PLS requires 2 stages to assess the Fit Model of a research model. These stages are as follows:

Figure 4. Structural Model (outer Model)

Evaluating Composite Reliability, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Cronbach Alpha

Evaluation of the measurement model with the square root of average variance extracted is to compare the AVE root value with the correlation between constructs. Good discriminant validity is achieved if the AVE root value is higher than the correlation value between the constructs. In addition, an AVE value greater than 0.5 is highly recommended.

Table 1. Goodness of Fit

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
PEOU	0.863	0.901	0.646
PU	0.831	0.887	0.663
CI	0.85	0.899	0.69

KP	0.844	0.896	0.682
PV	0.903	0.922	0.596

Source: Data processing with PLS, 2023

The AVE values for the four constructs are greater than 0.5 so it can be concluded that the evaluation of the measurement model has good discriminant validity. In addition to the construct validity test, a construct reliability test was also carried out which was measured by the criteria test, namely composite reliability and Cronbach alpha from the indicator block that measures the construct. A construct that is declared reliable if the value of composite reliability or Cronbach alpha is above 0.70. So, it can be concluded that the construct has good reliability.

Evaluasi Goodness of Fit

Goodness of Fit (GoF) is a measure of the overall fit of the model and is considered as a single measure of the outer model and the inner model. The results of the GoF calculation can be seen in table 2 below:

Table 2. Goodness of Fit Model

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	R Square
PEOU	0.646	
PU	0.663	
PV	0.69	0.637
KP	0.682	0.599
CI	0.596	0.565
Rata - rata	0.6554	0.600333

Source: Data processing with SmartPLS, 2023

$$\text{Gof} = \sqrt{\text{AVE} \times \text{R}^2}$$

$$\text{Gof} = \sqrt{0.5922 \times 0.6003}$$

$$\text{Gof} = 0,6772 \text{ (62,72\%)}$$

The GoF calculation result is 62.72 or 62.72%. This shows that the model obtained is good for making predictions. This means that the model has a high ability to explain empirical data.

Inner Model

Figure 5. Structural Model (Inner Model)

Testing of the inner or structural model is carried out to see the relationship between the significance value construct and the R-square of the research model. The structural model was evaluated using the R-square for the dependent construct, the t-test, and the significance of the structural path coefficients. The significance of the estimated parameters provides beneficial information about the relationship between the research variables. In PLS, statistical testing of each hypothesized relationship is conducted using a simulation. In this case, the bootstrap method was carried out on the sample. Testing with Bootstrap is also intended to minimize the problem of abnormal research data. The results of testing with bootstrapping from the PLS analysis are as follows:

Table 3. Path Coefficient (Mean, T-Values)

Hypothesis	Connection Variable	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Description
H1	PU -> PV	0.495	6.702	0.000	Signifikan
H2	PEOU -> PV	0.345	4.615	0.000	Signifikan
H3	PU -> KP	0.470	6.269	0.000	Signifikan
H4	PEOU -> KP	0.397	5.439	0.000	Signifikan
H5	PU -> CI	0.163	2.210	0.028	Signifikan
H6	PEOU -> CI	0.245	2.950	0.003	Signifikan
H7	PV -> CI	0.259	2.790	0.005	Signifikan
H8	KP -> CI	0.246	2.771	F2020.006	Signifikan

Source: Data processing with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on Table 3, the following results were obtained:

The structural equation obtained is;

$$PV = 0,495 PU + 0,345 PEOU$$

$$KP = 0,470 PU + 0,397 PEOU$$

$$CI = 0,163 PU + 0,245 PEOU + 0,259 PV + 0,246 CI$$

3.2 Discussions

The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Perceived Value

The study results found that Perceived Usefulness positively and significantly influences Perceived Value. The results align with previous research by Fernandes & Guerra, 2019; Guerra, 2015. In research conducted by Guerra entitled Purchase Intention on Online Content Services: An Application to the Music Streaming Services conducted in 2015 using the TAM (Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness) model variable has a significant influence on Perceived Value. In this study, it is agreed that Netflix is an application that is easy to use anywhere and anytime as long as there is an internet network. Netflix also has various features according to user preferences. So that users feel comfortable with this application and improve their feelings (mood). Therefore, Netflix can captivate its users according to the Usefulness of its application. Agree with Fernandes & Guerra (2019) are continuing the research on the TAM model in online music applications; the rating given by customers is an assessment based on the experience and usability of a particular product or service. In the context of this study, the evaluation of the Netflix application is based on the application interface and its primary uses. If both can improve the user experience, then the user will give a positive assessment Guerra (2015).

The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Customer Satisfaction

The study results found that Perceived Usefulness positively and significantly affects customer satisfaction. The research results are in line with previous research conducted by Cheah et al. (2021), with the research object using a mobile payment application, Lim (2017) with the research object being a subscription music online application; the third study was found that Perceived Usefulness as a variable can have a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. New Netflix users are interested in the app because their role models influence them. The activities carried out in the environment around Netflix users are a form of satisfaction felt by Netflix subscribers. When satisfied, they will recommend this application to the people around them. This means that the user's positive experience regarding how the application works can lead to positive feelings, exceeding the user's thought expectations.

The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Perceived Value

The results of the study found that Perceived ease of use has a positive and significant influence on Perceived value. The research results are in line with previous research conducted by Haba et al., 2017; with the research title "Factors Leading to Consumer Perceived Value of Smartphones and its Impact on Purchase Intention" with the aim of finding the impact of consumer perceived value (CPV) on smartphone purchase intentions among working Malaysian professionals. This study intends to find out whether social value, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, economic value and brand image have a direct or indirect effect on smartphone purchasing decisions. Whereas in C. Wang's research, 2014, entitled "Antecedents and consequences of perceived value in Mobile Government continuance use: An empirical research in China". The results of this study contribute to drawing attention to the important role of Perceived Value in m-government Continuance Intention and provide new insights that complement existing technology acceptance research. The value of the application that is obtained with the convenience offered is a combination that is in accordance with consumer preferences for the product. Netflix as an entertainment service provider is in accordance with the preferences expected by Netflix customers. Netflix is considered to have maintained its quality consistently. So that new users can easily learn and use the application. In the digital industry, especially in the Netflix application, user convenience in operating the application is an absolute consideration. When the user has a positive experience with the interface

(view) of the application, the user tends to have a good cognitive response. This cognitive response is referred to as perceived value.

The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Customer Satisfaction

The results of the study found that Perceived Ease of Use has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. The research results are in line with previous research conducted by Ohk et al., 2015; entitled "The Influence of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Interactivity, and Ease of Navigation on Satisfaction in Mobile Applications" with the results of Perceived usefulness, Interactivity and Perceived ease of use have a significant effect on Consumer Statistics. In research conducted by T Shah & Attiq, 2016; with the title "Impact of Technology Quality, Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness in the Formation of Consumer's Satisfaction in the Context of E-learning" and Tu et al., 2012 with the title "Perceived Ease of Use, Trust, and Satisfaction as Determinants of Loyalty in e-Auction Marketplaces". The easy use of the application makes the Netflix application enjoyable for all groups. Netflix users believe that the system adopted by Netflix makes it easy for users, so they don't need more effort to use it. The convenience offered by Netflix has received a positive response from customers. They are satisfied with the ease of use. This customer satisfaction is one of the follow-up responses after a cognitive assessment. Satisfaction is often associated with the affective aspect, which plays a psychological role as an emotional response.

The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention

The results of the study found that Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant influence on Continuance Intention. The research results are in line with previous research conducted by Camilleri & Falzon, 2020; Faqih, 2016; Hampton-Sosa, 2019; Hasan, 2017. However, there are differences in the results of this study with previous research by C. C. Lee & Lim, 2019; Leowarin & Thanasuta, 2021; Pal & Triyason, 2018. Netflix customers also agree that perceived usefulness can generate an intention to make repeat purchases and recommend to people around their environment. It is known that the Netflix application does have the ultimate goal of loyalty or the intention to continue using the application. As Camilleri & Falzon (2020) has stated that a website or digital application that users want is one that is appropriate to the user's wishes. This is known as perceived benefit. If the perceived usefulness is good, then the customer will be loyal in subscribing to the application. This potential loyal customer is good for Netflix to take advantage of in finding new customers.

The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention

The study results found that Perceived Ease of Use positively and significantly influences Continuance Intention. The research results align with previous Research conducted by Faqih, 2016; Hassan, 2017; C. C. Lee & Lim, 2019; Leowarin & Thanasuta, 2021. Hasan's Research, 2017, entitled "Analysis of Factors Affecting Willingness to Subscribe," uses the TAM model as a variable. Review on Video On Demand Netflix" The ease of use of the features felt by Netflix customers makes this application even more existent. They are evidenced by the increasing number of new and old customers who have made repeated purchases.

The Effect of Perceived Value on Continuance Intention

The study results found that Perceived Value positively and significantly influences Continuance Intention. The research results align with previous Research conducted by Lien et al., 2011; Singh et al., 2021. Research conducted by Singh et al., 2021; entitled "Assessing determinants influencing continued use of live streaming services: an extended perceived value theory of streaming

addiction." Netflix has a reasonably high application rating; this proves that the features owned by Netflix are by consumer preferences. Thus, many Netflix users make repeat purchases.

The Effect of Customer Satisfaction on Continuance Intention

The study results found that customer satisfaction positively and significantly influences Continuance Intention. The research results align with previous Research conducted by Hsu et al. (2021), Pratiwi & Dwiyanto, 2019; Sik & Lee (2010). Customer satisfaction is a form of attitude expected by the company. Satisfied consumers have many positive impacts, one of which is loyal customers. Creating loyal customers is due to the form of satisfaction consumers feel. As is the case with Netflix users, on average, they become loyal thanks to the satisfaction with this application that has been used.

The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention Through Perceived Value

The study results found that Perceived Value has a significant influence in mediating Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention. The research results align with previous Research conducted by (Fernandes & Guerra, 2019; Guerra, 2015). Both studies stated that perceived value could mediate the relationship between perceived usefulness and streaming subscription loyalty. Netflix users intend to renew subscriptions based on perceived usefulness and value.

The Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention Through Customer Satisfaction

The results of the study found that customer satisfaction has a significant influence in mediating Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention. The research results are in line with previous Research conducted. The Research in question was conducted by (Hsu et al., 2021; Shah & Attiq, 2016), in which customer satisfaction can mediate the relationship between perceived usefulness and streaming subscription satisfaction.

The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention Through Perceived Value

The study's results found that Perceived Value significantly influences Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by research, which states that customer satisfaction can be a mediating variable related to the relationship between perceived ease of use and continuance intention. The research in question was conducted by Haba, Hassan, & Dastane (2017); this study stated that perceived value could mediate the relationship between perceived ease of use and streaming subscription loyalty.

The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention Through Customer Satisfaction

The results of the study found that customer satisfaction has a significant influence in mediating Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention. The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by (Ohk, Park, & Hong, 2015; Tu, Fang, & Lin, 2012), where in this study, it was stated that perceived value could mediate the relationship between perceived ease of use and streaming subscription loyalty.

4. Conclusion

Perceived Usefulness has a positive and significant effect on Perceived Value. Perceived Usefulness can increase Customer Satisfaction with the Netflix application customers. Perceived Ease of Use has a significant effect on Perceived Value. Perceived Ease of Use can increase the Perceived Value felt by subscribers of the Netflix application. Perceived Ease Of Use can increase the satisfaction felt by Netflix application customers. Perceived Usefulness can increase Continuance Intention

directly on Netflix application subscribers. The increasing Perceived Ease of Use will directly and significantly increase the Continuance Intention felt by customers. Increasing Perceived Value will significantly affect the increase in Continuance Intention felt by customers. Quality value, social value, emotional value, and price value can be increased to increase the customer's Continuance Intention. Customer satisfaction has a significant effect on Continuance Intention. The Significant Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention through Perceived Value. The Significant Effect of Perceived Usefulness on Continuance Intention through Customer Satisfaction. The Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention through Perceived Value. The Significant Effect of Perceived Ease of Use on Continuance Intention through Customer Satisfaction.

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